

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN THE ARMED FORCES

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Abstract. *This article talks about the importance of spiritual and educational work carried out in the Armed Forces of our country.*

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As stated by the President, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the next extended meeting of the Security Council held at the National Defense Management Center of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 13, 2022, "Ensuring information security in the current situation where there is a sharp struggle in the global information space, it is important to protect young people from foreign ideas, to strengthen the psychological training and fighting spirit of military personnel" [1].

At a time when international relations in some regions are becoming more and more complicated, about 40 of more than 200 countries have various national-ethnic, religious disagreements, and various conflicts between peoples and states are deepening, and even the danger of nuclear threats is increasing, peacekeeping and stability are the main factors of our country's policy. that the principles are in place is shown by the large-scale reforms carried out by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev. Uzbekistan is strengthening trade, economic, social and political cooperation not only with Central Asia, but also with the countries of the world from a strategic point of view. The love of the people living in our society for the Motherland is manifested through mother's love and father's courage. Homeland is the soil where the umbilical blood of a person is shed, a blessed place that brings him to maturity and gives meaning to his life. We glorify the Motherland through the great legacy and unforgettable memory left from ancestors to generations. A person who lives with the feeling of the Motherland is proud and proud, and his goals and objectives are clear. The prosperity of the country and the peace of the country are a priceless blessing. At all stages of human development, humanity has been striving for peace and harmony. The Uzbek people highly value peace and stability. He knows that it is a guarantee that his dreams will come true. That is why every citizen living in this country protects the right to live freely and prosperously. By being loyal to the motherland, respecting the heritage of the ancestors, and being worthy of the whole of humanity, he approaches every big and small task with responsibility. Thus, strengthening the borders of the country, strengthening the inviolability of our borders, fighting against internal and external threats always calls for awareness. Therefore, the government of Uzbekistan had its own army from the first days of independence. Today, it is the duty of every person living in this country to strengthen the independence of our Motherland, protect its peace and ensure its stable development. In this regard, the issue of youth is at the top. The reason is that in today's modern conditions, serious attention is being paid to the priority issues of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism. That's why young people brought up in the spirit

of military patriotism are ready to lay down their lives for the peace of their country. If the feeling of patriotism does not prevail in the hearts of people, they cannot be trusted in any field.

To turn our national army into a school of bravery, fortitude and courage of the youth, to inculcate in the consciousness of the citizens that service to the Motherland is the highest happiness, and in this way, both the ordinary stone and the ordinary stone on the soil of the Motherland are sacred. The concept that it is the greatest happiness to be worthy of our ancestors who breathed the memory of the homeland must become our main idea. Therefore, on November 22, 1993, the Presidential Decree "On the Combat Flag of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was signed, and a single example of the combat flag of the Armed Forces was established. According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Establishing the Day of Defenders of the Fatherland" of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 1993, "January 14 - Day of Defenders of the Fatherland" was declared. The military doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was adopted in August 1995, defined the military policy of the country, which was only 4 years old after its independence. Based on the military and political situation in the region, the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted on February 3, 2000. On January 9, 2018, the new version of the Law on the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan was signed. The doctrine consists of 4 sections and 40 points, which cover general rules, military-political, military-strategic, and military-economic aspects.

The military doctrine forms the basis of the defense policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. National security is a component of the whole-state concept and is based on completely new approaches to foreign policy, interstate relations, and problems of war and peace. Also, the reliable defense capability of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the high combat capability of the Armed Forces are the most important principles for the development of economic, political, strategic and military-technical and scientific power, the cohesion of the people of Uzbekistan and the education of every citizen in the spirit of patriotism. Also, on February 23, 2018, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approving the concept of educating young people in the spirit of military patriotism" was adopted.

Decision PQ-3898 of August 4, 2018 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the fundamental improvement of the system of raising the moral and educational level of the military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and the Armed Forces introduced on this basis In accordance with the concept of increasing the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in the system of forces, "The Motherland is sacred, it is an honorable duty to protect it!" idea was put forward. Also, in the Armed Forces system, every Friday of the week is designated as the "Day of Moral Elevation and Patriotism", and it is necessary to encourage the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. The goal is to faithfully protect the sovereignty, territorial integrity, and peace of our people.

Wide-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to strengthen peace and stability, ensure human rights, freedoms and interests, comprehensively develop our country, and raise its prestige in the international arena.

Therefore, according to the seven priority directions defined in the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2022-2026, the state program "Glorification of human dignity and active neighborhood year", "Prosperous village", "Prosperous neighborhood", "Every

family is an entrepreneur", "Youth is our future" ", "Five Positive Initiatives" as part of important programs and plans, based on the meaning and content of the reforms, the main ideological principles of this decree put the human factor in a high position. Today, educating the youth of our country in the spirit of military patriotism is one of the most important tasks.

Our great compatriots, who lived in our great past, protected our country from invaders in order to maintain the peace of our people, and bravely fought against the enemy for the freedom of the Motherland - Shiroq, Tomaris, Spitamen, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Temur Malik, Najmuddin Kubro, Amir Temur. we are always proud to lead by example. Currently, our Armed Forces have improved significantly in terms of organization and structure.

The mobility of structures, combat capability, and physical and moral readiness of the military have increased. Military units and divisions were provided with modern weapons and combat equipment. The work being carried out to fill our national army with professional personnel, to further improve the training, knowledge and skills of military personnel is commendable.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev on January 12, 2021 at the regular meeting of the Security Council to pay attention to the work carried out within the framework of the tasks assigned and the socio-economic and moral-educational condition of military personnel serving in military units emphasized.

Representatives of military science also join the ranks of this category of people, and with their research, they make an individual contribution to ensuring defense and security.

The head of our state made it a task to constantly pay attention to the improvement of the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. Emphasizing that the scope of work on the organization of military-patriotic and spiritual-educational activities aimed at increasing the sense of pride of the military personnel in their national and cultural heritage on the example of the great thinkers of the Uzbek people in the troops of the Ministry of Defense should not be reduced from the agenda, "A military without military knowledge" there will be no knowledge," he said.

The issues of social protection of military personnel, adjustment of family conditions, provision of housing are being implemented step by step.

As the Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of the President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has defined, "Strengthening the security and defense potential of our country, conducting an open, pragmatic and active foreign policy" is an important direction.[2]

In conclusion, the sense of patriotism is strengthened by understanding, feeling and understanding the military field. That's why we believe that it is necessary to teach a subject related to the military field once a week in three stages of continuous education. These are in schools, secondary and higher educational institutions...

The essence of the large-scale reforms implemented under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev calls people to understand and feel the human factor in life and internal possibilities more deeply, and not to shy away from work.

The spiritual and physical maturity of citizens, especially the youth of the country, combined with feeling, understanding, learning and understanding of high civic responsibility through the idea of national development, peace and well-being of the country, as well as a sense of belonging to the society, will be a solid foundation for the realization of our great goals.

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